

Open Science at TU/e

White Paper

Introduction

At TU/e, Open Science has been declared a strategic priority within the Strategy 2030 document. To effectively realize the objectives of this priority, TU/e proposes to create a practical and achievable Open Science Agenda. This White Paper is a proposal for the TU/e Open Science agenda. Its priority areas were derived from the [National Program Open Science Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda](#) (NPOS).

Open Science will be a combined effort involving both primary research and service departments, taking into consideration disciplinary specific needs and requirements.

Context

In 2017, commissioned by the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (OCW), the first NPOS was published.

At the international level, the European Commission promotes open scholarly communication and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research outputs are central.

Open Education has been a significant focus in Dutch higher education with strong support from OCW. Dutch universities adopted [Declaration on Open Educational Resources](#), aiming to direct the development, sharing and reuse of educational resources.

Scope of the White Paper

Based on the (inter)national agenda, Open Science themes of relevance for TU/e are: Open Access publishing; Open and FAIR data; Open Education; and Collaboration with external partners (societal engagement, industry). These themes are crucial for

aligning our university's research practices with broader scholarly objectives and national agenda. Central to advancing Open Science practices is the effort of rewarding researchers through Recognition & Rewards, making Open Science accessible through Skills & Training, and establishing Open Science as the norm through Community Engagement & Communication and the implementation of Policies & Guidelines.

Open Access Publishing

In 2022, TU/e provided read access to all peer-reviewed journal articles published by our researchers that year. The expectation is that also in 2024 and the following years, we will be able to offer 100% reading access to this publication type.

(Inter)national Open Access agenda broadens to reuse and rights retention for all publication types

The [National Program Open Science](#) (NPOS) not only aims for read access, but also *"to remove barriers to creating, reading, reusing and evaluating all Dutch scholarly output."* In addition, it is the ambition of the NPOS to not only provide open access to peer-reviewed scientific articles, but also to conference proceedings, book chapters and books. Many [European research funding bodies](#) (including NWO) have underlined the importance of open availability of all publications with a license that allows reuse.

The European Union [has the added ambition](#) to address the cost of open access publishing. The EU believes that *"so-called Article Processing Charges (APCs) far exceed the actual cost of publication. This deepens inequalities among researchers and institutions, with many being unable to afford APCs."*

To align with these evolving standards, the following priorities could be considered for the next 2-year period:

- Develop a new Open Access Policy: guidelines on

embargoes, copyright, publishing rights

- Expand open access provision to conference proceedings, books and book chapters
- Extend publishing deals to full Open Access journals and support academic-led publishing.

Open and FAIR Data

In the [Strategy 2020-2024](#), the EU expressed the ambition to make Open Data using FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) principles the default. In addition, they formulated a few Open Science ambitions that are instrumental, or even conditional, to achieve this ambition:

- Open Science activities should be part of the **quality judgment** of research
- **New rewards** must be implemented for academics to engage in Open Science
- Publicly funded research should adhere to the international standards of **Integrity and Reproducibility**
- Academics must have the **skills and support** to enable Open Science

[NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda](#) attaches a deadline to this ambition: 2030. And, like the EU, it formulates prerequisites that are conditional to the success of the FAIR data agenda – infrastructure, policies & regulations, and support & training.

To align with these evolving standards, the following priorities could be considered for the next 2-year period:

- Develop institutional and department specific data management policies to facilitate the implementation of FAIR principles
- Develop a user-friendly research data infrastructure and monitoring mechanism to facilitate implementation of FAIR principles

Open Education

In Dutch higher education, Open Educational Resources (OER) offers tailored education to students. In March 2022 a [Declaration on Open Educational Resources](#) was adopted by Dutch universities. The ambition of the declaration is that the Dutch higher education institutions direct the creation, sharing, reuse and procurement of digital and Open Educational Resources and the associated or derivable

data.

TU/e shares this ambition and successfully implemented these through the [4TU Applied Mathematics Institute](#) (4TU.AMI) open repository project and the Open Educational Resources shared in Edusources in the context of the TU/e [BOOST! program](#).

To align with evolving standards, the following priorities could be considered for the next 2-year period:

- Develop an open education vision and policy
- Develop infrastructure that will significantly improve the integration and use of OER, and enhance access to platforms and cloud storage

Collaboration with external partners

TU/e has the ambition to be among the leading universities in science & technology, creating responsible innovations and contributions to societal challenges in tight-knit collaborations with society and industry. Therefore, valorization is of utmost importance to us, making scientific insights available and usable to industry and society. TU/e Strategy 2030 recognizes the importance of collaboration with society and states that in our industry collaborations, we strive for maximal disclosure of results and findings, while acknowledging that protection can be necessary.

Preliminary results of a LIS study into existing practices and opportunities in societal engagement show that next to industrial partners, our academics also work closely with citizens. TU/e has a clear profile on how its research is connected to society; the impact achieved via multi-stakeholder partnerships and collaborations is visible within the TU/e and beyond. TU/e aims to provide academics with the necessary support to foster partnerships and collaborations.

Societal engagement and collaboration with industry are also included in NPOS and the Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) and is encouraged by research funders like NWO and the European Union.

Industry and university interests may diverge in terms of sharing research output. Part of the Open Science agenda is to examine these diverging interests and determine where joint steps towards further sharing of

research results can be taken.

To align with evolving standards, the following priorities could be considered for the next 2-year period:

- TU/e should increase visibility of Societal Engagement across the university and investigate what support is needed to practice it.
- TU/e needs a working process to include the extent of research data disclosure in our agreements with industry.

Make Open Science rewarding through Recognition and Rewards

In late 2019, the Dutch public knowledge institutes and research funds published a position paper that argues that the system of recognizing and appreciating academics needs modernization. The position paper is later detailed in a roadmap [“Room for everyone’s talent in practice: how we are shaping a new system of Recognition and Rewards”](#).

In the period 2020-2022, a task force worked on a TU/e vision that is the starting point for the new academic career policy. The foundations of the vision, as well as the resulting preliminary development matrix and bibliographical sketch were thoroughly discussed with several academic stakeholders at several points in time.

Open Science is believed to contribute to replicability, transparency, efficient use of resources and results and therefore to high quality research and innovation. It is included in both the national priorities and the leading principles of the TU/e vision on recognition and rewards to acknowledge the time investment of researchers in practicing Open Science.

To make Open Science rewarding, the following priorities could be considered for the next 2-year period:

- Make Open Science an integral part of development, assessment and promotion of academics.
- Address Open Science activities in the performance management cycle (Annual Reviews).

Make Open Science easy through Skills & Training

Incorporating Open Science into everyday research and education practice requires specific knowledge and skills. This is recognized by both the NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda, and by the Strategic Evaluation Protocol in the PhD training and policy sections.

TU/e trains both PhDs and academic staff. Currently, structural Open Science training is offered only to PhD students through PROOF [training program](#). While appreciated and evaluated highly (scoring 8.0), the course's attendance is low; possibly due to its voluntary nature, the workload, or its visibility.

In addition to PROOF, LIS offers on-demand workshops on various aspects of Open Science, ranging from an introduction to Open Science, training on funding requirements, data management, and open access publishing. To ensure that both academic and research support staff are well-informed about Open Science and its implications, TU/e's Research Support Network (RSN) introduced RSN Academy in 2023 which covers a range of topics, including Open Science.

TU/e invests in talent development, creating an environment that enables academics to perform excellent research. By equipping academics with necessary Open Science skills, TU/e broadens societal impact and fosters a research community that values openness.

To make Open Science accessible, the following priorities could be considered for the next 2-year period:

- Embed Open Science training modules in the existing Academic Staff Training Program and UTQ
- Make PROOF course on Open Science more visible and increase attendance.

Make Open Science the norm through Community Engagement & Communication

The NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda states that *“the transition towards an open academic culture requires lively networks of Open Science Communities of academics, support staff and interested non-academics in different domains, both*

national and international, to create awareness of the Open Science principles and practices.”

One critical role in the transition to Open Science is played by Open Science Communities (OSCs) — bottom-up networks of Open Science-minded academics, support staff and students. This is evident by the growing number of OSCs in the Netherlands and abroad, as well as support provided by institutions and Open Science NL. TU/e established its Open Science Community in 2019; which raises awareness and educates on Open Science practices, fostering knowledge sharing through events, workshops and meetings.

TU/e recognizes the importance of the bottom-up adoption of Open Science and is committed to supporting and encouraging knowledge sharing and collaboration within the TU/e community. Given the already demanding agendas of the academics, participation in the bottom-up initiatives, such as OSC/e, should be appreciated and recognized. To fully achieve the goals of this Agenda, we recognize the need to expand and increase the visibility of Open Science throughout TU/e.

To make Open Science the norm, the following priorities could be considered for the next 2-year period:

- Open Science should be more visible on the TU/e website, in onboarding procedures and during events.
- TU/e should encourage OCS/e membership and support the community both financially and organizationally.

Make Open Science Normative through Policies & Guidelines

Policies and guidelines, providing frameworks, tools and incentives could play a role in making Open Science a norm. At the national level, NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda takes responsibility for several key areas: monitoring and assessment of Open Science practices, harmonization of funding instruments, advancement of infrastructure for scholarly communication and research data management. Policies at the local level could connect

with these national developments.

To make Open Science normative, the following priorities could be considered for the next 2-year period:

- Develop a new Open Access policy to further TU/e’s ambition to openly share all publications.
- Develop institutional and departmental data policies to promote the sharing of research data and provide tailored instructions.
- Develop and implement an Open Education policy to facilitate evidence-informed creation, sharing, and reuse of digital learning materials, and to link with the developing Recognition and Rewards program.